

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF ARCHEOLOGY, ETHNOGRAPHY, SOURCE STUDIES AND HISTORIOGRAPHY IN THE COVERAGE OF WORLD HISTORY

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Abstract. The article describes how important the role of special historical disciplines is in highlighting the facts and hypotheses of world history. Archeology, ethnography, source studies and historiography are auxiliary historical sciences that are very important for revealing historical secrets

Key words. historical discipline, past, sources, auxiliary, archeology, ethnography.

Introduction. Archeology is a historical discipline that studies the historical past of mankind from material sources. The history that archaeologists study, primitive society includes more than 99% of the human past, from the Paleolithic to the emergence of literacy in societies around the world. The basic principle of archeology, any human activity leaves a trace. And in these footsteps it is possible to explain the former essence of that time. Most often, archaeologists study the ancient history of people, when writing did not yet exist or it did not illuminate all aspects of the life of ancient people. Ethnography is a science that studies ethnic peoples and ethnic formations, their origin, composition, settlement, cultural and everyday features, and material and spiritual cultures. Ethnography studies everything related to the peoples of the world. Source study is an auxiliary science of historical sources as historical and cultural phenomena. The main object of source study is historical sources. Historiography in the narrow sense of the word - a set of studies in the field of history, devoted to the definitions of a topic or historical era, or a set of historical works that have internal unity in ideological, linguistic or national terms.

Method. The task of archeology is to discover sources during excavations. Sources found during excavations are studied by source experts and ethnographers and historiographers. Ethnographers study the subject from what angle? They study what kind of people they used for what purposes and what changes this source led to. And source experts carefully investigate the whole essence of this source to which period it belongs and compare it with other sources. Historiographers study discovered sources to determine the date and reasons for use and record them in books and journals to preserve them in history.

Results. Because we study history based on historical sources. The importance of historical disciplines for the study, knowledge of history is very important. It is impossible to study history in one direction, because all areas of history need each other's help. An archaeologist who discovers a historical object or inscription needs the help of a linguist and others. Only by combining the knowledge of scientists from different fields can one come to the right decision. The main part of history is primitive, in which there was no language and writing. to study the history of this period, special historical sciences help us

Discussion. Archaeology helps us to appreciate and preserve our shared human heritage. It informs us about the past, helps us understand where we came from, and shows us how people lived, overcame challenges, and developed the societies we have today. The focus of archaeology has changed over the years. Archaeologists today study everything from ancient

pots to DNA to theories of cognitive processes.¹ This expanded scope of archaeology has necessitated the creation of many new interpretive approaches and recovery techniques. Archaeologists help reconstruct the past in other ways besides simply excavating sites belonging to a particular culture. Ethno archaeologists study people living today and record how they organize and use objects. The study of modern behavior can help reveal how and why people in the past left behind certain types of remains in certain patterns. Environmental archaeologists help us understand the conditions that existed when the people being studied were alive. Experimental archaeologists reconstruct techniques and processes used in the past to create artifacts, art, and architecture. Underwater archaeologists study material remains that survive underwater, including shipwrecks and sites inundated by a rise in sea level

Conclusion. When we talk about culture, we mean the behavior and beliefs of groups of people. These cannot be excavated directly, although they influence the physical remains, material culture, that archaeologists find. These remains range from stone tools to buildings to written records. Features are remains that cannot be moved (large buildings, post holes), while artifacts are smaller, portable objects. Ethnography: This approach mainly focuses on a particular community. It is more of a kind of close field observation and basically tries to study a socio cultural phenomena. For example, judging others based on the researchers' cultural standards. Ethnography can be used for comparative analysis of cultural groups (e.g. eating habits of North Indians and South Indians), also known "Ethnology". Further it can also be used to analyses the cultural past of group of people (e.g. Harrapan civilisation), also known as "Ethnohistory".

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